

Minkowski addition implies Relativity

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The relativistic transformation connecting moving inertial frames - unlike the classical variant - avoids infinities. This is because speeds follow Einstein addition:

$$v \oplus w = (v + w)/(1 + vw/c^2)$$

where c is the upper-bound speed of light; this an early example of 'renormalization' [1]. Although c is merely an upper bound, it cannot formally be a variable [2], hence it is a constant.

Einstein addition actually comes almost for free. Let $E(v)$ be a relativistic transformation:

$$E(v) = \gamma \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -v \\ -v/c^2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

where

$$\gamma = \gamma(v) = (1 - v^2/c^2)^{-1/2}$$

is the usual Lorentz factor. Composing two frames moving with speeds v and w leads to the matrix product $E(v)E(w)$ which satisfies the group/addition property [3]

$$E(v \oplus w) = E(v)E(w)$$

Of course, Einstein addition is a hyperbolic **identity** in disguise:

$$\tanh(x + y) = \frac{\tanh(x) + \tanh(y)}{1 + \tanh(x)\tanh(y)}$$

Now, Minkowski [4] derived a hyperbolic version of the relativistic transformation using a 'double imaginaries' method. His matrix is

$$H(x) = \begin{pmatrix} \cosh(x) & \sinh(x) \\ \sinh(x) & \cosh(x) \end{pmatrix}$$

The group/addition property here is immediate:

$$H(x)H(y) = \begin{pmatrix} \cosh(x + y) & \sinh(x + y) \\ \sinh(x + y) & \cosh(x + y) \end{pmatrix} = H(x + y)$$

Conversely, suppose a non-zero matrix $Q(x)$ of the form

$$Q(x) = \begin{pmatrix} a(x) & b(x) \\ b(x) & a(x) \end{pmatrix}$$

satisfies the Minkowski group/addition property; does it follow that $Q(x) = H(x)$? Let's see.

By assumption

$$Q(x)Q(y) = Q(x + y)$$

hence

$$Q(x)Q(0) = Q(x)$$

which forces

$$Q(0) = I_2$$

so that

1. $a(0) = 1$
2. $b(0) = 0$

and further

$$3. Q(x)Q(-x) = Q(0) = I_2$$

hence

$$4. Q^{-1}(x) = Q(-x)$$

From 3.

$$\det(Q(x))\det(Q(-x)) = 1$$

so that either

$$A. \det(Q(x)) = \det(Q(-x)) = -1$$

or

$$B. \det(Q(x)) = \det(Q(-x)) = 1$$

Now, if A. holds

$$a^2(x) - b^2(x) = -1$$

so in particular

$$a^2(0) - b^2(0) = -1$$

contradicted by 1. & 2.

Hence

$$5. \det(Q(x)) = 1$$

or

$$6. a^2(x) - b^2(x) = 1$$

From 4. and 5.

$$Q^{-1}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} a(x) & -b(x) \\ -b(x) & a(x) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a(-x) & b(-x) \\ b(-x) & a(-x) \end{pmatrix}$$

Equating components now yields

$$7. a(x) = a(-x), \text{ so } a(x) \text{ is even}$$

and

$$8. b(x) = -b(-x), \text{ so } b(x) \text{ is odd}$$

Altogether then, 6., 7., and 8. are solved by

$$a(x) = \cosh(x)$$

$$b(x) = \sinh(x)$$

Hence indeed

$$Q(x) = H(x)$$

Minkowski group/addition **by itself** has led to the relativistic transformation in hyperbolic form; the Einstein form is recovered in the usual way [5].

The moral here is that Special Relativity actually solved a **one-off** problem: **infinite speeds**.

- [1] <https://zenodo.org/records/6954316>
- [2] <https://zenodo.org/records/10161185>
- [3] <https://zenodo.org/records/3540985>
- [4] <https://zenodo.org/records/3547714>
- [5] <https://zenodo.org/records/3525985>